

European Nucleotide Archive

Data Retrieval

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ENA Background

ENA Background: What is ENA?

Open platform for the management, sharing, integration and dissemination of sequence data

- **Globally comprehensive scientific record** and European node of **INSDC**
- **Broad scope** covering raw data, through layers of interpretation and context
- **Connectivity** with broader EMBL-EBI resources
- Sequence data **foundation**
- Rich submission, discovery and retrieval **software, tools and services**
- **Support** through Helpdesk and training
- **Management**, sharing, integration and dissemination of sequence data
- **Data coordination** including project-specific data hubs and portals

Archive

Platform

Submitting data to the ENA

Why is it important to share data?

- Findability
- Accessibility
- Reproducibility/Reusability
- Interoperability
- Community collaboration
- Data standards

Maximum value

Submitting data to the ENA

All data in the ENA is submitted by members of the research community

What motivates people to submit?

- Open data
- Reproducibility
- Reusability
- 3rd party access
- Archival
- **Publication**
- Downstream analyses

*The data lifecycle, from ELIXIR Europe
<https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>*

Data resources at EMBL-EBI

ENA - an ELIXIR Core Data Resource

- The ENA is part of the wider ecosystem of biodata resources
- Recognised as an ELIXIR CDR and Global Core Biodata Resource by the Global Biodata Coalition
- Integration into a system of biodata resources increases value in genomics data

GLOBAL
CORE
BIODATA
RESOURCE

ENA Data Model

ENA Data Model

- ENA stores huge amounts of data
 - ... from many users
 - ... with samples from many taxa
 - ... who use many different techniques
 - ... and sequence on many different platforms
- But we need to display data in a consistent manner
- A robust data model is the first step in achieving this

ENA Data model

Sequence data is organised into tiers:

- **Reads:** raw sequence data
- **Assemblies:** reconstructions of actual replicons
- **Annotations:** interpretations of biological function

Annotation and **assembly** are frequently paired

ENA Data Model

- A FASTQ file is an example of data from the read tier:

```
@SRR2960126.1 1/1
GCCAGCTATATCAGTTTCCTTTGTGATGGGGCGTTTATGTAAGGGATGGGTATGGAAGTGCACCCTGGCTAGAACGAAAAGACTTGCTAT
TGTAAGTTA
+
=;?AD=D?FDB???ACGHGGEHCEEHC@GDG>GDGHFF@9?C<38BFEACHIID>EEC>A3@D;?=-;ABCA?
@@A8=8=B>89>ACCCACCADC3@4@@A
@SRR2960126.2 2/1
GTGGGTAACATTTGGAACAGAAAAACAAAAGTAGAATGGTGGGTGGAGGAGAACAATAAAAATGATACTTCATTTAATTATCATTTAGA
GATGTATATC
+
CCCFDFFHHHHHIIJIIJJJJJJJJJJII?
DGIJJJJBFIHFGGGIJJIIJJJJHHHHHFFFFFFFDEEEEDFEDEEEDDEEEDDDDDDEEFFDD
@SRR2960126.3 3/1
CTTTAACAAAGATTTTTTAAAAAATGCTGTGCTGTAATCACTAGCAAAAACCTAATTTGCTAGTTGCATTGGAAAGATATTGATACT
TGACAATTTA
+
CCCFDFFHDDFFGHHHJIIJJIIJJJJIIJGHHIIJJJJIIJJJJJJJJIGIHHHHHFFFFFFFEDCCADCDEEEDDDDD
DDDDDDDDDD
@SRR2960126.4 4/1
GCTTTTTTTCGGCAACGATGGAATCGATCAATTGTTATTGTGACAGCTAAATTTGATAAAACAAAATGATACAGTTTCAAAGTATCAAAA
ATTTGCAGCA
+
@=?DDDBDFBHD<FBHAHBD@FGIEDHGH?BB9BFGHIDF@===FCGEGGGH3AEHC;@DDF@C>;A@AC:
5-5;>@C@CCC:>@ACCB@C:4>;(2
```

ENA Metadata Model

ENA Metadata Model

- Data without any context has no value
- Metadata tells us how sequence data was produced
- Makes it possible to compare datasets:

“I want to retrieve data from bacteria ...

... in the Atlantic Ocean ...

... sampled between 50-100m ...

... between April and July ...

... compared with the same from the Indian Ocean”

- Archives have spent a lot of time thinking about this!

ENA Metadata Model

Study

ENA Webin Submissions Portal [Support](#) [Manage Account](#) [Logout \(Webin-\)](#)

Register study (project)

Submission Details

Release date [This is when your study will be made public.] *
01-03-2027

Viral Studies in Bees

Will you provide functional genome annotation ?

PubMed Citations Registration

Add PubMed Citations +

PubMedId	Title
PPR8996	Investigating the viral ecology of global bee comm

Sample

Mandatory Fields

Selection	Field Name	Validation	Units
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NCBI Taxonomy	Text field	None
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Scientific name	Text field	None
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Sample alias (unique name)	Text field	None
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Sample title	Text field	None
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Sample description	Text field	None
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	collection date	Regular expression	None
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	geographic location (longitude)	Regular expression	DD
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	geographic location (country and/or sea)	Permitted values	None

Optional Fields

Metadata Model: Sample Checklists

- ENA metadata checklists guided by standards working groups and the communities
 - Keep up with requirements within communities
- Rich standardised metadata facilitates linking to source information
- General minimum requirements (INSDC)
 - Organism information mandatory and linked with NCBI taxonomy
 - INSDC spatiotemporal policy: mandatory provision of collection date & geographic location
 - INSDC missing value reporting

INSDC spatiotemporal metadata – minimum standards update (03-03-2023)

[Home](#) > [News & Announcements](#) > [INSDC spatiotemporal metadata – minimum standards update \(03-03-2023\)](#)

INSDC continues its aim to increase the number of sequences for which the origin of the sample can be precisely located in time and space through harmonisation of accurate geographical annotation and date and time of collection information.

ENA Metadata Model

Raw reads/experiments

Mandatory Fields			
Selection	Field Name	Field Label	Permitted Value
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample	Sample	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	study	Study	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	instrument_model	Instrument model	Permitted values
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_name	Library name	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_source	Library source	Permitted values
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_selection	Library selection	Permitted values
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_strategy	Library strategy	Permitted values
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_layout	Library layout	Permitted values
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	forward_file_name	Forward file name	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	forward_file_md5	Forward File checksum	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	reverse_file_name	Reverse file name	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	reverse_file_md5	Reverse file checksum	

Analyses

```
STUDY PRJEB12345
SAMPLE ERS123456
ASSEMBLYNAME annotated_assembly
ASSEMBLY_TYPE isolate
COVERAGE 21.0
PROGRAM NovaSeq v1.2.3
PLATFORM NovaSeq 6000
MOLECULETYPE genomic DNA
RUN_REF ERR123456
FLATFILE annotated_assembly.embl.gz
```

ENA Metadata Model

Microbial occurrence and symbiont detection in a global sample of lichen metagenomes

Gulnara Tagirdzhanova, Paul Saary, Ellen S. Cameron, Carmen C. G. Allen, Arkadiy I. Garber, David Díaz Escandón, Andrew T. Cook, Spencer Goyette, Veera Tuovinen Nogerius, Alfredo Passo, Helmut Mayrhofer, Håkon Holien, Tor Tønsberg, [...], Toby Spribille [view all]

Published: November 7, 2024 • ht

Architecture, Chromatin and Gene Organization of *Toxoplasma gondii* Subtelomeres

by Susana M. Contreras ¹

¹ Laboratorio de Parasitología Molecular, Instituto Tecnológico Chascomús (INTECH), Universidad Nacional de General San Martín (UNSAM), Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas (CONICET), Chascomús 7130, Argentina

Metadata Model: New Discoveries from Old Data

- Polyomavirus – “*many tumours*”
- Well known in mice and primates, including humans
- Taxonomic classification for a viral family can guide research to faster understand new member viruses
- But previously, few polyomaviruses were known

Cryo-EM structure of BK polyomavirus, PDBj

Metadata Model: New Discoveries from Old Data

- Buck *et al.* report discovery of new polyomaviruses in fish, cows, and sheep
- Sequence searches against INSDC data identified likely new species in the genomes of 7 invertebrates
- A near-complete polyomavirus in the genome of the Baja Californian bark scorpion

Bark scorpion

Photo credit: Joel Sartore

ENA Browser

ENA Metadata Model: Results

Project description and metadata

Project: [PRJNA407112](#)

The ecology of bee viruses is complex, as viruses are readily shared among bee species and plants. However, our understanding of bee viral communities is primarily derived from studies of North America and European *Apis mellifera* honey bee populations. Here, we develop a novel pipeline to rapidly, inexpensively, and robustly screen for bee viruses. This pipeline includes purification of encapsulated RNA/DNA viruses, sequence-independent amplification, high throughput sequencing, integrated assembly of contigs, and screening through a series of filters to identify contigs specifically corresponding to viral sequences. We evaluated samples of honey bees and co-foraging non-*Apis* bee species (12 bee species in total) from 9 countries and 5 continents. We identified sequences corresponding to (-)ssRNA, (-)ssRNA, dsRNA, and ssDNA viruses. Overall, 127 contigs corresponding to novel viruses (previously not observed in bees), with 29 represented by >0.1% of the reads in a given sample. These 29 contigs corresponded to 9 viral families, including 6 viral families that have not been previously observed in bees. These viruses and viral families were distributed across multiple regions and species. This study provides a robust pipeline for analysis of insect viruses, and greatly expands our understanding of the diversity of viruses found in bee communities.

Show More

Organism: [insect metagenome](#)

Secondary Study Accession: SRP117625

Study Title: Investigating the viral ecology of global bee communities with high-throughput metagenomics

Center Name: Columbia

Study Name: insect metagenome

ENA-REFSEQ: N

PROJECT-ID: 407112

ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC: 2017-09-15

ENA-LAST-UPDATE: 2023-05-19

Read Files

Show Column Selection

Download report: [JSON](#) [TSV](#) [Get download script](#) [Download selected files](#)

Study Accession	Sample Accession	Tax Id	Scientific Name	Generated FASTQ files: FTP	SRA files: FTP
PRJNA407112	SAMN07634932	1234904	insect metagenome	<input type="checkbox"/> SRR6033667.fastq.gz	<input type="checkbox"/> SRR6033667
PRJNA407112	SAMN07634933	1234904	insect metagenome	<input type="checkbox"/> SRR6033668.fastq.gz	<input type="checkbox"/> SRR6033668
PRJNA407112	SAMN07634924	1234904	insect metagenome	<input type="checkbox"/> SRR6033675.fastq.gz	<input type="checkbox"/> SRR6033675
PRJNA407112	SAMN07634949	1234904	insect metagenome	<input type="checkbox"/> SRR6033691.fastq.gz	<input type="checkbox"/> SRR6033691
PRJNA407112	SAMN07634953	1234904	insect metagenome	<input type="checkbox"/> SRR6033662.fastq.gz	<input type="checkbox"/> SRR6033662

Run-centric data table

General

View: XML
XML (STUDY)

Download: XML
XML (STUDY)

Cross References: Show

ORCID Data Claims: Show

Related ENA Records: Show

Navigate around the object

Data

Read Files: Hide

Wgs Files: Show

Navigate on data

Tags

xref

EuropePMC

Information for a single run

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home>

ENA Metadata Model: Navigation Bar

- View project metadata
- Show/hide different information about project
- Explore cross-references related to project
- Explore reads/analyses files

General

View:	XML
	XML (STUDY)
Download:	XML
	XML (STUDY)
Cross References:	Show
Publications:	Show
ORCID Data Claims:	Show
Related ENA Records:	Show

Data

Read Files:	Hide
Wgs Files:	Show

ENA Metadata Model: Results

Organism: [insect metagenome](#)

Secondary Study Accession: SRP117625

Study Title: Investigating the viral ecology of global bee communities with high-throughput metagenomics

Center Name: Columbia

Study Name: insect metagenome

ENA-REFSEQ: N

PROJECT-ID: 407112

ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC: 2017-09-15

ENA-LAST-UPDATE: 2023-05-19

Related ENA Records

Result	Count
Experiment	37
Assembly	1
Genome assembly contig set	1
Run	37

ENA Metadata Model: Results

Experiment: SRX3183290

Illumina MiSeq sequencing; Kenya (Naivasha)

Organism: [insect metagenome](#)
Experiment Accession: SRX3183290
Instrument Platform: ILLUMINA
Instrument Model: Illumina MiSeq
Center Name: SUB3040496
Library Layout: SINGLE
Library Strategy: WGS
Library Source: METAGENOMIC
Library Name: KNN3
Library Selection: RANDOM PCR

Show More

Read Files

Show Column Selection

Download report: [JSON](#) [TSV](#)

Get download script

Download selected files

Download All

Study Accession	Sample Accession	Experiment Accession	Run Accession	Tax Id	Scientific Name	Generated FASTQ files:	Sub
PRJNA407112	SAMN07634953	SRX3183290	SRR6033662	1234904	insect metagenome	<input type="checkbox"/> SRR6033662.fastq.gz	

General

View: [XML](#)

Download: [XML](#)

Cross References: [Show](#)

ORCID Data Claims: [Show](#)

Data

Read Files: [Hide](#)

Tags

environment by geolocation

terrestrial

freshwater

New tags feature

Annotations of ENA objects

Controlled textual annotations provided to metadata objects to facilitate search and filtering

ENA Metadata Model: other features

Navigation & Cross References

- Taxon:
[Taxon:1234904](#)
- EuropePMC:
[PMC5995813](#) →
- MGnify:
[MGYS00005464](#) →
- WGS:
[PEHZ0100000](#) →

Organism:	insect metagenome
Secondary Study Accession:	SRP117625
Study Title:	Investigating the viral ecology of global bee communities with high-throughput metagenomics
Center Name:	Columbia
Study Name:	insect metagenome
ENA-REFSEQ:	N
PROJECT-ID:	407112
ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC:	2017-09-15
ENA-LAST-UPDATE:	2023-05-19

Publications

Publications citing this record

Investigating the viral ecology of global bee communities with high-throughput metagenomics.

Galbraith DA, Fuller ZL, Ray AM, Brockmann A, Frazier M, Gikungu MW, Martinez JFI, Kapheim KM, Kerby JT, Kocher SD, Losyev O, Muli E, Patch HM, Rosa C, Sakamoto JM, Stanley S, Vaudo AD, Grozinger CM.

Department of Entomology, Center for Pollinator Research, Huck Institutes of the Life Sciences Pennsylvania State University, University Park, PA, USA. dag5031@gmail.com.

Sci Rep 8(1): 8879 (2018 Jun)

[Show abstract](#)

[Unpaywall \(pdf\)](#)

[DOI \(doi\)](#)

[Europe_PMC \(html\)](#)

[Europe_PMC \(pdf\)](#)

ENA Metadata Model: other features

Cross-reference Search

The ENA Xref service holds cross-references to a number of external data resources linked to ENA records. These cross-reference sources include both services operated by colleagues at EMBL-EBI (such as UniProt and Ensembl) as well as those operated outside EMBL-EBI (including SILVA and RFAM).

The update and frequency of each source is dependent on their own release cycle and/or internal processes, with ENA supporting updates as frequently as once a week.

These cross-references can also be explored programmatically using the Xref API.

If you would be interested in registering your resource as part of our cross-reference service, you can request to be added as a new Xref source here and a member of the team will get into contact with you to discuss your eligibility.

Search by Source Search by ENA record Source Details

Xref Source: Accession: Target: Expanded: Search

EMBL-EBI | MGnify

MGnify

Submit, analyse, discover and compare microbiome data

Overview Submit data Text search Sequence search Browse data About Help

Home > Studies > MGYS00005464

Study MGYS00005464

Investigating the viral ecology of global bee communities with high-throughput metagenomics

Overview Analysis summary

Last updated: Fri May 22 2020

Map Satellite

External links

- ENA website (SRP117625)

Organism: [insect metagenome](#)

Secondary Study Accession: [SRP117625](#)

Study Title: Investigating the viral ecology of global bee communities with high-throughput metagenomics

Center Name: Columbia

Study Name: insect metagenome

ENA-REFSEQ: N

PROJECT-ID: 407112

ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC: 2017-09-15

ENA-LAST-UPDATE: 2023-05-19

Navigation & Cross References

- Taxon: Taxon:1234904
- EuropePMC: PMC5995813
- MGnify: MGYS00005464
- WGS: PEHZ01000000

Data Retrieval at ENA

Finding Sequences by Metadata: Text Search

Text Search

Uses EBI Search to perform a free text search across ENA data. For more detailed usage please refer to the [help & documentation section](#).

Search term: human kinase

Search Q

Search results for human kinase

Sequence	Sequence View all 38,807 results.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">Sequence (38,807)Sequence (Standard) (38,807)	X59932 Human mRNA for C-SRC-kinase
Coding	Sequence (Standard) View all 38,807 results.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">Coding (202,809)Coding (CON) (28,816)Coding (Standard) (13,395)Coding (WGS) (162,598)	X59932 Human mRNA for C-SRC-kinase
Non-coding	Coding View all 202,809 results.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">Non-coding (1)Non-coding (CON) (1)Non-coding (Standard) (1)Non-coding (WGS) (1)Non-coding (TSA) (1)Non-coding (TLS) (1)	HBO89504 Alistipes sp. (human gut metagenome) thymidylate kinase
Read	Coding (CON) View all 28,816 results.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">Experiment (583)Run (360)	GAP42981 Lentimicrobium saccharophilum badF-type ATPase, related to human N-acetylglucosamine kinase
Study	Coding (Standard) View all 13,395 results.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">Study (1,141)Project (1,936)	CAA43372 Homo sapiens (human) human protein kinase B
Sample	Coding (WGS) View all 162,598 results.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">Sample (361)	HBO89504 Alistipes sp. (human gut metagenome) thymidylate kinase
About	Non-coding
<ul style="list-style-type: none">ENA (112)	GU186386.1.1.2135.ncRNA Homo sapiens (human) endothelium-specific receptor tyrosine kinase 1 (tie-1) antisense RNA
	Non-coding (CON)
	GU186386.1.1.2135.ncRNA Homo sapiens (human) endothelium-specific receptor tyrosine kinase 1 (tie-1) antisense RNA
	Non-coding (Standard)
	GU186386.1.1.2135.ncRNA Homo sapiens (human) endothelium-specific receptor tyrosine kinase 1 (tie-1) antisense RNA
	Non-coding (WGS)
	GU186386.1.1.2135.ncRNA Homo sapiens (human) endothelium-specific receptor tyrosine kinase 1 (tie-1) antisense RNA
	Non-coding (TSA)
	GU186386.1.1.2135.ncRNA Homo sapiens (human) endothelium-specific receptor tyrosine kinase 1 (tie-1) antisense RNA
	Non-coding (TLS)
	GU186386.1.1.2135.ncRNA Homo sapiens (human) endothelium-specific receptor tyrosine kinase 1 (tie-1) antisense RNA
	Experiment View all 583 results.
	ERX4701109 Illumina HiSeq 4000 sequencing: 3' UTR RNA-sequencing of oncogene-driven human cancer cell lines treated with a kinase inhibitor versus controls
	Run View all 360 results.
	ERR12146189 Illumina NovaSeq 6000 sequencing: Single-cell RNA-seq of human cancer cell lines and their resistant variants treated with cytostatic kinase inhibitors
	Study View all 1,141 results.
	SRP318118 RIPK1 kinase-dependent gene expression in human astrocytes in vitro

- Enter terms into search box at ENA page
- Prone to false positives
- Good if you already know what you're looking for

Finding Sequences by Metadata: Advanced Search

The image shows three overlapping screenshots of an advanced search interface, illustrating the steps to build a query:

- Top Screenshot (Step 1):** Shows the 'Data Type' selection screen. The 'Data type' dropdown is set to 'Nucleotide sequences'. A red arrow points from this step to the second screenshot.
- Middle Screenshot (Step 2):** Shows the 'Query' field with the text 'tax_eq(9606)'. Below it, a filter panel is open for 'NCBI Taxonomy', showing 'Homo sapiens' selected. A red arrow points from this step to the third screenshot.
- Bottom Screenshot (Step 3):** Shows the final query: 'tax_eq(9606) AND description="kinase"'. The filter panel is now set to 'Description' with 'kinase' entered. A red arrow points from this step to the right.

Focus your search on:

- Specific data type
- Particular taxon
- Restricted description
- Leverage annotated fields

Finding Sequences by Metadata: Advanced Search

- Advanced search builds URLs which contain the query:

Data type: ?

2 Query 3 Inclusion/Exclusion 4 Fields

Query:

Build Query ?

AND OR + Add rule + Add group

NCBI Taxonomy = Delete

Include subordinate taxa

NCBI taxonomic classification

- ```
curl -X POST -H "Content-Type: application/x-www-form-urlencoded" -d 'result=sequence&query=tax_eq(9606)%20AND%20description%3D%22kinase%22&fields=accession%2Cdescription%2Ctax_id&format=tsv' "https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/portal/api/search"
```

AND OR + Add rule + Add group

Description =  Delete

brief sequence description

# Finding Sequences by Metadata: Advanced Search

|                          |                                                                                                              |                      |
|--------------------------|--------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------|----------------------|
| <a href="#">U39065</a>   | Human MAP kinase kinase 6b mRNA, complete cds.                                                               | <a href="#">9606</a> |
| <a href="#">U39064</a>   | Human MAP kinase kinase 6 mRNA, complete cds.                                                                | <a href="#">9606</a> |
| <a href="#">L05624</a>   | Homo sapiens MAP kinase kinase mRNA, complete cds.                                                           | <a href="#">9606</a> |
| <a href="#">BD292228</a> | Antisense modulation of MAP kinase kinase 6 expression.                                                      | <a href="#">9606</a> |
| <a href="#">HV547376</a> | JP 2011234724-A/6: REGULATION OF A KINASE, REGULATED IN COPD KINASE (RC KINASE).                             | <a href="#">9606</a> |
| <a href="#">BC010464</a> | Homo sapiens mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase kinase 3, mRNA (cDNA clone IMAGE:4179950).              | <a href="#">9606</a> |
| <a href="#">BC143224</a> | Homo sapiens mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase kinase 3, mRNA (cDNA clone IMAGE:9051725).              | <a href="#">9606</a> |
| <a href="#">BC043010</a> | Homo sapiens mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase kinase 9, mRNA (cDNA clone IMAGE:6048901).              | <a href="#">9606</a> |
| <a href="#">HV547371</a> | JP 2011234724-A/1: REGULATION OF A KINASE, REGULATED IN COPD KINASE (RC KINASE).                             | <a href="#">9606</a> |
| <a href="#">BC040716</a> | Homo sapiens mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase kinase 9, mRNA (cDNA clone IMAGE:6047608).              | <a href="#">9606</a> |
| <a href="#">HV547375</a> | JP 2011234724-A/5: REGULATION OF A KINASE, REGULATED IN COPD KINASE (RC KINASE).                             | <a href="#">9606</a> |
| <a href="#">AK222781</a> | Homo sapiens mRNA for mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase kinase 11 variant, clone: HEP01062.            | <a href="#">9606</a> |
| <a href="#">HV547372</a> | JP 2011234724-A/2: REGULATION OF A KINASE, REGULATED IN COPD KINASE (RC KINASE).                             | <a href="#">9606</a> |
| <a href="#">AK312714</a> | Homo sapiens cDNA, FLJ93116, Homo sapiens mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase kinase 13 (MAP3K13), mRNA. | <a href="#">9606</a> |
| <a href="#">AB044546</a> | Homo sapiens B/OKcl.13 mRNA for mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase kinase, partial cds.                 | <a href="#">9606</a> |



# Finding Sequences by Metadata: Advanced Search

Advanced search builds URLs which contain the query:

- Adult Japanese firefly squid from Toyama Bay:

..."**result=sample**&query=**tax\_eq(6624)**%20AND%20**country%3D%22\*Toyama%20Bay\***%22%20AND%20**dev\_stage%3D%22adult**%22&format=tsv" ...

- Find PacBio read data consisting of >100,000 base pairs:

..."**result=read\_run**&query=**instrument\_platform%3D%22PACBIO\_SMRT**%22%20AND%20**base\_count%3E100000**&format=tsv" ...

# Finding Sequences by Metadata: Advanced Search

|    | A             | B                | C           | D            | E          | F           | G           | H                                                                  | I                                 |
|----|---------------|------------------|-------------|--------------|------------|-------------|-------------|--------------------------------------------------------------------|-----------------------------------|
| 1  | run_accession | sample_accession | accession   | first_public | country    | fastq_aspi  | fastq_bytes | fastq_ftp                                                          | fastq_galaxy                      |
| 2  | ERR1146215    | SAMEA3678241     | SAMEA367824 | 26/01/2016   | United Kin | fastp.sra.e | 3577849;745 | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR114/005/ERR1146215/ERR1146215_1.fe | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR1 |
| 3  | ERR1146216    | SAMEA3678242     | SAMEA367824 | 26/01/2016   | United Kin | fastp.sra.e | 3376195;700 | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR114/006/ERR1146216/ERR1146216_1.fe | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR1 |
| 4  | ERR1146217    | SAMEA3678243     | SAMEA367824 | 26/01/2016   | United Kin | fastp.sra.e | 1008769;209 | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR114/007/ERR1146217/ERR1146217_1.fe | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR1 |
| 5  | ERR1146218    | SAMEA3678244     | SAMEA367824 | 26/01/2016   | United Kin | fastp.sra.e | 3071458;631 | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR114/008/ERR1146218/ERR1146218_1.fe | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR1 |
| 6  | ERR1146219    | SAMEA3678245     | SAMEA367824 | 26/01/2016   | United Kin | fastp.sra.e | 1432972;303 | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR114/009/ERR1146219/ERR1146219_1.fe | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR1 |
| 7  | ERR1146220    | SAMEA3678246     | SAMEA367824 | 26/01/2016   | United Kin | fastp.sra.e | 1538163;320 | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR114/000/ERR1146220/ERR1146220_1.fe | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR1 |
| 8  | ERR1146221    | SAMEA3678247     | SAMEA367824 | 26/01/2016   | United Kin | fastp.sra.e | 2338039;491 | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR114/001/ERR1146221/ERR1146221_1.fe | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR1 |
| 9  | ERR1146222    | SAMEA3678248     | SAMEA367824 | 26/01/2016   | United Kin | fastp.sra.e | 2938737;632 | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR114/002/ERR1146222/ERR1146222_1.fe | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR1 |
| 10 | ERR1146223    | SAMEA3678249     | SAMEA367824 | 26/01/2016   | United Kin | fastp.sra.e | 2497149;536 | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR114/003/ERR1146223/ERR1146223_1.fe | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR1 |
| 11 | ERR1146224    | SAMEA3678250     | SAMEA367825 | 26/01/2016   | United Kin | fastp.sra.e | 802500;1645 | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR114/004/ERR1146224/ERR1146224_1.fe | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR1 |
| 12 | ERR1146225    | SAMEA3678251     | SAMEA367825 | 26/01/2016   | United Kin | fastp.sra.e | 4418537;932 | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR114/005/ERR1146225/ERR1146225_1.fe | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR1 |
| 13 | ERR1146226    | SAMEA3678252     | SAMEA367825 | 26/01/2016   | United Kin | fastp.sra.e | 2228667;480 | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR114/006/ERR1146226/ERR1146226_1.fe | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR1 |
| 14 | ERR1146227    | SAMEA3678253     | SAMEA367825 | 26/01/2016   | United Kin | fastp.sra.e | 1731368;380 | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR114/007/ERR1146227/ERR1146227_1.fe | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR1 |
| 15 | ERR1146228    | SAMEA3678254     | SAMEA367825 | 26/01/2016   | United Kin | fastp.sra.e | 3010345;616 | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR114/008/ERR1146228/ERR1146228_1.fe | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR1 |
| 16 | ERR1146229    | SAMEA3678255     | SAMEA367825 | 26/01/2016   | United Kin | fastp.sra.e | 2950320;635 | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR114/009/ERR1146229/ERR1146229_1.fe | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR1 |
| 17 | ERR1146230    | SAMEA3678256     | SAMEA367825 | 26/01/2016   | United Kin | fastp.sra.e | 1798224;376 | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR114/000/ERR1146230/ERR1146230_1.fe | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR1 |
| 18 | ERR1146231    | SAMEA3678257     | SAMEA367825 | 26/01/2016   | United Kin | fastp.sra.e | 4863879;105 | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR114/001/ERR1146231/ERR1146231_1.fe | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR1 |
| 19 | ERR1146232    | SAMEA3678258     | SAMEA367825 | 26/01/2016   | United Kin | fastp.sra.e | 2822547;564 | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR114/002/ERR1146232/ERR1146232_1.fe | ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR1 |

# Advanced Search: New Tags Feature

- Tags available on the bottom right of records.
- Take users to advanced search and query records with same tag.
- Example: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/SAMEA104307802>

# ENA Portal API

- A REST API which can help you build advanced queries:

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/portal/api/>

| Search & Discovery |                  | Endpoints for searching across metadata                             | ^   |
|--------------------|------------------|---------------------------------------------------------------------|-----|
| GET                | /search          | Perform a warehouse search                                          | 🔒   |
| POST               | /search          | Perform a warehouse search with POST                                | 🔒   |
| GET                | /count           | Count rows matching search parameters                               | 🔒   |
| POST               | /count           | Count rows matching search parameters                               | 🔒   |
| GET                | /searchFields    | Get a list of searchable fields for a result type                   | ⌵   |
| GET                | /returnFields    | Get a list of fields that can be returned for a result type         | ⌵   |
| GET                | /results         | Get a list of available result types (data sets) to search against. | ⌵   |
| GET                | /links/taxon     | Taxonomy links                                                      | ⌵   |
| GET                | /links/study     | Study links                                                         | ⌵   |
| GET                | /links/sample    | Sample links                                                        | 🔒 ⌵ |
| GET                | /fileReportCount | Get row count for file report from warehouse search                 | 🔒   |
| GET                | /fileReport      | Get file report from warehouse search                               | 🔒   |
| GET                | /doc             | Download the documentation as a PDF file                            | ⌵   |
| GET                | /controlledVocab | Get a list of available values for a controlled vocabulary field    | ⌵   |

- Reports in JSON or TSV, which can be used as input for data requests
- Basis of developments such as the new browser
- Documentation:  
<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/portal/api/doc>

# Tools for Downloads

- ENA Browser Tools
- ENA File Downloader
- Browser API

# ENA Browser Tools

- A set of Python scripts available through GitHub:

<https://github.com/enasequence/enaBrowserTools>

- Type in an accession and get data:

```
> enaDataGet -f fastq -d <destination/directory> -m ERR164409
```

```
> enaGroupGet -f submitted -d <destination/directory> SAMEA2591084
```

- Easily scriptable – integrate with pipelines

```
DGKS604AGG7V:~ holt$ enaDataGet ERR2763139
Downloading file with md5 check:ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/ERA157/ERA1579672/bam/RNA-seq_BL79_BR1.bam
Downloading file with md5 check:ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/ERA157/ERA1579672/bam/RNA-seq_BL79_BR1.bam.bai
Completed
DGKS604AGG7V:~ holt$
```

# ENA File Downloader



- GUI application to get your data for you:  
<https://github.com/enasequence/ena-ftp-downloader>
- Provide an accession to get its data
- Provide a full query to get its results

# ENA APIs

- [Browser API](#): Programmatically fetch data using accessions or data type. Can be used to download ENA Records in EMBL flat file, fasta or XML format dependant on the record type.
- [Xref API](#): holds cross-references to a number of external data resources linked to ENA records.

The image shows a list of ENA API endpoints. The top section lists three POST endpoints for bulk data retrieval in XML, FASTA, and EMBL formats, each with a maximum limit of 10,000 accessions per request. Below these are two GET endpoints for individual record retrieval in XML and versions. The bottom section shows two groups of endpoints: TSV and JSON, each with four GET endpoints for target, source, searchcount, and search operations.

|      |                       |                                                                                       |
|------|-----------------------|---------------------------------------------------------------------------------------|
| POST | /xml                  | Obtain records in XML format with max limit of 10000 accessions per request           |
| POST | /fasta                | Obtain records in FASTA file format with max limit of 10000 accessions per request    |
| POST | /embl                 | Obtain records in EMBL flatfile format with max limit of 10000 accessions per request |
| GET  | /xml/{accession}      | xml                                                                                   |
| GET  | /versions/{accession} | versions                                                                              |

  

| TSV |                  | Get Cross references in tab separated value format |
|-----|------------------|----------------------------------------------------|
| GET | /tsv/target      |                                                    |
| GET | /tsv/source      |                                                    |
| GET | /tsv/searchcount |                                                    |
| GET | /tsv/search      |                                                    |

  

| JSON |                   | Get Cross references in JSON format |
|------|-------------------|-------------------------------------|
| GET  | /json/target      |                                     |
| GET  | /json/source      |                                     |
| GET  | /json/searchcount |                                     |
| GET  | /json/search      |                                     |

# Globus

- Globus provides a more user-friendly, feature-rich directory interface for interacting with the FTP server.
- Globus also provides a command line interface (CLI) which can be used without access to a graphical user interface environment.



# Other Data Download options

- wget

<ftp://ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR164/ERR164407/ERR164407.fastq.gz>

- curl -o ERR164407.fastq.gz

'<ftp://ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk/vol1/fastq/ERR164/ERR164407/ERR164407.fastq.gz>'

- Command-line FTP client:

```
ftp ftp.sra.ebi.ac.uk
Name: anonymous
Password:
ftp> cd vol1/fastq/ERR164/ERR164407
ftp> get ERR164407.fastq.gz
```

- ascp -QT -l 300m -P 33001 -i path/to/aspera/installation/etc/...

**Thank you!**

**Any questions?**



# Practical Session: Data Retrieval

You will be using some of our tools to find data:

1. Build search queries using the ENA Advanced Search
1. Build search queries using the ENA Portal API
1. Download XML files using the ENA Browser API
1. Retrieve private metadata submitted by you using ENA Reports API